

ANALYSIS OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES AT "SAM AUTO" JSC

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Abstract. *In this article, the development of the market concept, planning, management, control and analysis of its development requires the implementation of marketing research and the statistical analysis of processes is considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, market, customer, demand, management, control, analysis, concept.*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the implementation of the new Uzbekistan strategy, the urgent issues of organizing marketing research to achieve the marketing goals and tasks of enterprises have been raised. The "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev has been developed and programs are being prepared for its implementation. Comprehensive measures are being implemented in our country for the active development of the digital economy, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and fields, first of all, in public administration, education, health care and agriculture..

Every enterprise produces a product or recommends a certain type of service to consumers. Many economic and social processes take place during the production process. With a statistics course, we study and analyze them in a simplified form. The object of our coursework was "SAM Auto". Many economic processes are taking place in JSC enterprise as well. Let's start with the history and activities of the company.

On October 30, 2006, the joint venture was reorganized into "SamAvto" LLC, the share of the Turkish side was bought by "UzAvtoSanoat". "UzAvtoSanoat" and "Isuzu" joined the founders of the newly established company, buses and trucks under the Isuzu brand began to be produced (since 2007). The models produced by the joint-stock company "Uzotoyol" were discontinued, and the production of 4 types of buses and 5 types of "Isuzu" trucks began. It was announced that spare parts service will be provided to "Uzotoyol" cars, which were previously manufactured by "Samavto", from the "Isuzu" company. The plant produces 5 types of buses and more than 40 types of trucks. This series includes Isuzu LE-60 low-floor city buses,

From 2009 to 2012 (before the opening of its own production facilities[3]), JV "SamAuto" JV MAN Auto-Uzbekistan, an Uzbek-German joint venture, also produced MAN trucks. According to the Land Rover Uzbekistan project, the Samarkand Automobile Plant was supposed to produce Land Rover off-road vehicles.

The production process is a set of actions of workers and tools, as a result of which raw materials, materials, semi-finished products and components entering the enterprise are transformed into finished products or services in a certain amount and with a certain property, quality and quality. range over a period of time. The production process consists of main, auxiliary and service processes.

The technical and organizational-economic description of the production process at the enterprise is determined by the type of product, the volume of production, the type and type of equipment and technology used, and the level of specialization.

The production process in enterprises is divided into two types: main and auxiliary. The main ones include processes directly related to the transformation of labor objects into finished products. For example, turning ore into metal by melting it in a blast furnace, or turning flour into dough and then into ready-baked bread.

Auxiliary processes: moving objects of work, repairing equipment, cleaning rooms, etc. Such works only help the main processes, but do not directly participate in them.

The main difference between the auxiliary processes and the main ones is the difference between the place of sale and the place of consumption. The main production products from which the main production processes are carried out are sold to consumers on the side in accordance with the concluded supply contracts. This product has its own brand, label and market price is set for it.

Products of auxiliary production, where auxiliary processes and services are performed, are consumed within the enterprise. The cost of maintenance and support work is entirely dependent on the price of the main product sold to consumers on the side.

The production process is divided into many elementary technological procedures, which are called operations. The production process is a part of the production process. It is usually performed in one workplace without reconfiguring the equipment and using the same set of tools. Like the production process itself, operations are divided into primary and auxiliary.

The following set of rules and methods are used to reduce the cost of production, organize the production process and increase its reliability:

specialization of sites, jobs;

continuity and correctness of the technological process;

parallelism and proportionality of production operations.

Specialization consists in the fact that each workshop, site, workplace is allocated a technologically homogeneous or fixed range of products. Specialization makes it possible to apply the principles of continuity, direct flow, the most economically useful methods of organizing production.

Continuity is the reduction or reduction of interruptions in the production of finished products to zero, in addition, each subsequent operation of the same process begins immediately after the completion of the previous one, which reduces the time of product production, reduces the downtime of equipment and workplaces. .

Directness describes the movement of labor objects in the production process and provides the shortest path from the workplace for each product.

Such a movement is characterized by the elimination of all return and counter movements during the production process, which helps to reduce transportation costs.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The rule of parallelism implies simultaneous execution of different operations in the production of the same product. This rule is especially widely used in series and mass production.

The rule of parallelism includes:

parallel (simultaneous) production of various aggregates and parts designed to complete (assemble) the final product;

simultaneous execution of various technological operations when processing the same parts and units on different parallel equipment.

From the point of view of saving costs, it is very important to observe certain ratios of the capacity (productivity) of the equipment fleet between the workshops and sections working on the production of products.

Joint-stock company "SAM AUTO" finished the year 2021 with the production of more than 50 billion 302 million soums. In 2022, the factory produced 31,052 pieces of high-quality machine products. 856 mln. Flour products worth 520,000 soms were produced. By 2022, 82% had been completed. In 2022, the automobile industry produced 61,426 buses this year. The introduction of additional raw materials into the production of buses increased the quality of buses and made them more affordable. 5,061 of the produced cars were produced as a heavy-duty truck based on consumer demand. In general, this plant will make 143 billion in 2022. 426 mln. Soum car was produced.

According to the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4058 of November 28, 2008 "On the program of measures to support enterprises of the real sector of the economy, ensure their stable operation and increase export potential" 5673.7 mln. to SAM AUTO joint-stock company by the joint-stock company "UZAVTOSANOAT" as part of the measure to reduce the production costs of assembly and repair machines. set at soum. This task is worth 5673 mln. 700,000 soums or 100% completed. 45121 in 2022. Automobile spare parts worth 147 thousand soums are produced and put on the market, and the year ended with a net profit of 141 billion 854 thousand soums.

Table 1

Economic indicators of "SAM AUTO" JSC for 2020-2021-2022.

No	Indicators	Die cho w unit	2020 is real	2021 is real	2022 is real	Growth rate 2021-2020		Growth rate 2022-2021	
						(+.-)	%	(+.-)	%
1	Cars at current prices	d	60111109	67885565	70998337	7774456	112.9	3112772	104.5
	At comparable prices	Ms	67738207	67873683	67805945	135476	100.2	-67738	99.9
2	Balance profit	Ms	1332924	1466216	1599570	133292	110.0	133354	109.0
3	Bus Products Total	d	67095	50375	58735	-16720	75.1	8360	116.6
	Cars	d	37694	30527	34111	-7168	81.0	3584	111.7
	Car spare parts	d	544	679	612	135	124.8	-68	90.1
4	Iron bodies	d	6315	6315	6315	0	100.0	0	100.0

5	Net profit	Ms	992200	1091420	1101810	99220	110.0	10390	100.9
	Including for the development of spent production	Ms	198440	218284	218362	19844	110.0	78	100.0
	For dividends	Ms	793760	873136	883448	79376	110.0	10312	101.1
6	Profitable. A balance between benefit and cost	%	1.5	1.5	1.5	1	99.4	0	100.0
7	Labor productivity	Ms	56522	61423	45277	72750	147.0	1414	101.3
8	Average monthly salary		489792	45446	578513	12747	115.8	11280	101.9
9	Annual average number of employees	pers on	796	659	728	-137	82.8	69	110.4
10	Salary fund	Ms	3867402	6806795	6337099	2939393	176.0	-469696	93.09
11	Use of factory capacity	%	61	67	66	6	110.0	-1	98.5
12	Use of additional power	%	57	67	62	10	118.2	-5	92.5

In order to save electricity, gas, water, fuel, lubricants, and manpower consumed in production, in order to save the power of the Community's workshops, in the 2nd decade, the workers are being responded to, and the workshops are being stopped. Mainly because of this, the data of the following tables 3-4 also confirm that the consumption of electricity, gas and water does not exceed the specified norm. This table shows the actual consumption of electricity, gas and fuel lubricants in 2020, 2021 and the amount of electricity required by factories in 2022 and the amount of fuel and lubricants expected to be consumed in 2022. . The joint-stock community has a sewage network with a length of more than 1.5 km. Sewage collected through sewers goes to T>H>U. From here, wastewater is sent to the water treatment plant through pumps. Since 2013, competitor "MAN" has managed to achieve 30% efficiency in sales volume.

Table 2

Electricity consumption in the main production plant in 2020-2022

No	The name of the workshops	Unit of measure	2020 year		2021 year		2022 year	
			Total cost	for 1 ton	Total cost	for 1 ton	Total cost	for 1 ton
1	Idolization	Kvt	7153705	114	7219335	120	7302500	130
2	Automotive industry	Kvt	1025137	28	1034542	35	1091250	39
3	Tire assembly	sq	167005	27	168538	30	318000	35

As can be seen from this table, the company's electricity consumption costs have been increasing over the years. We will perform certain actions to forecast the amount of his spending in 2020.

Table 3

Information on fuel and lubricants spent in 2020-2021 and the plan for 2022

No	Type of fuel and lubricants	Unit of measure	2020 year	2021 year	Difference (+.-)	2022 plan
1	Compressed gas	m ³	25860	28446	2586	25600
2	Liquefied gas	Liter	12950	14245	1295	11500
3	Diesel fuel	Liter	6500	7150	650	8000
4	Diesel is 10V	Kg	600	660	60	2500
5	Gasoline	Liter	0	0	0	0
6	Ind M 20A	Liter	0	0	0	300

"SAM AUTO" JSC receives grain and produces family, bus and heavy-duty vehicles from it. In addition to this, the enterprise also produces spare parts for cars and additional equipment. The company has been operating for almost 50 years and has done a lot of work. The number of employees in the enterprise is regularly increased. After all, there is also the task of providing employment to our people.

Table 4

The number of employees at "SAM AUTO" JSC in 2021

No		Unit of measure	2021 year			
			1 quarter	2 quarters	3 quarters	4 quarters
1	Total number of employees	person	6745	7014	7195	7657
2	The number of workers in production	person	5147	6424	5547	5258
3	Including workers who create products	person	1365	1542	1456	1567
4	The number of employees not related to production	person	200	452	452	450

In 2021, the number of employees is set at 7,657, and it is necessary to increase this figure in 2022 and the following years. After all, the population of our country is growing every year. Employment of young people is very important. If we take into account that the number of employees not related to production has not changed in recent years, we can know that the work in the field of administrative management is in a constant state.

We saw that the provision of wages to the workers in the society was also implemented at a positive level. In the following table, we see the table of the total wage fund in 2021.

Table 5

Total salary fund in 2021

No		Unit of measure	2021 year				Total
			1 quarter	2 quarters	3 quarters	4 quarters	
1	Total number of employees	m. soum	1853149 4	1873741 7	1997284 5	1906669 86	7630878 60
2	The number of workers in production	m. soum	1422620 2	1430108 3	1538675 6	1458178 86	5842495 90
3	Including workers who create products	m. soum	3743735	3893498	4062452	3942421 6	1562003 90
4	The number of employees not related to production	m. soum	561569	542847	561756	5436284	2206588 0

The total amount of salary is 763087860 thousand soums. In the next table, we see the average salary estimate. Increasing the monthly salaries of every employee is included among the strategic tasks of the enterprise. This means raising the wages of each employee in a competitive society and, as a result, increasing the size and breadth of the employees' consumption basket.

Table 6

Nomenclature of products of "SAM AUTO" JSC intended for production in 2021

No	Product types	Unit of measure	2021 year				Total
			1 quarter	2 quarters	3 quarters	4 quarters	
	Main product types						
1	Buses	tn	816500	516500	616000	916500	1265500
2	Cargo carrier	tn	89000	89200	89500	89800	2437500
3	Heavy load carrier	tn	7520	7600	7645	10600	2110600
4	Spare parts	mln. d	27424	28975	30452	35740	105245

And we see that buses have a growth rate between quarters. Spare parts were received by the end of the year.

CONCLUSION

In short, if every industrial enterprise develops its marketing strategy in a thorough and scientifically based manner, the future activity of that enterprise will be very good.

In an economy based on market relations, the market is welcome. And the market requires management. For this, it is necessary to apply marketing together with several market mechanisms. Because the development of the market concept requires the implementation of marketing research to plan, manage, control and analyze its development. Marketing research, in turn, is carried out through statistical analysis of these processes.

Getting timely and complete information about the customer - his needs, problems, perceptions and characteristics of the purchase decision process - is essential for business success. The main task of marketing management is to apply an understanding of the customer and his problems at all stages of strategic planning and thus become an "expert" on the customer.

A key strategic concept in marketing is related to the value proposition - a unique way of conveying information about the advantages of the company and its products to customers. A value proposition is the core of a company's positioning statement, the "why" part of the who-what-what paradigm. Value Proposition "Why should customers buy from you and not from your competitors?" is the answer to the question.

Market-to-market analysis examines the strengths and weaknesses of a company's competencies and resources in comparison to its competitors. Competitor analysis focuses on exploring customer needs, their requests, and acceptance of the company's offering, but not enough on what the company can do better than its competitors.

Research planning is a process of determining the company's potential opportunities and supporting the strategic alignment of the company's capabilities with changing external environmental conditions. The goal of the strategy is the optimal allocation of the company's resources. Strategic planning "looks ahead" and helps the company adapt to rapidly changing market conditions, thus requiring management to develop organized, agile plans and forecasts. These plans help the company to notice and adapt to changes in the external environment before others.

Research planning begins with an assessment of the company's strengths and weaknesses. All areas of the company's operations, including organizational structure, financial capabilities, technical competencies, location, production capacity and equipment, management and other personnel, distribution system and relations with distributors, sales force performance, company image, customer loyalty, pricing strengths, advertising and sales promotion skills, etc. should be evaluated.

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